

Newsletter Vol. 2

SEPTEMBER 2024

Welcome to the 2nd CUSTODES Newsletter!

This edition brings you the latest updates on our progress, showcasing the milestones we have reached and the advances made in enhancing security and safeguarding critical infrastructures.

Join us as we share key achievements and explore how our work continues to drive innovation in cybersecurity and data protection.

Enjoy and don't forget to follow us online (if you are not doing it already), for more immediate updates!

Our Latest Highlights

CUSTODES 1st Video

Events

CUSTODES at CyberHOT 2024 Summer School

CUSTODES actively participated in the **CyberHOT 2024 Summer School**, held on September 9 -10, 2024, in Athens, Greece. The event was organised by the **CyberSecurity Lab** of the **University of Piraeus**, **Focal Point SPRL** from Belgium, the **Microprocessor and Hardware Lab** at the **Technical University of Crete**, **Trustilio** from the Netherlands, and **Dienekes** from the **Technical University of Crete**.

CUSTODES at the 30th ICE IEEE/ITMC International Conference

Dr. Jasmin Cosic presented the paper “**Deciphering Cyber-Security Certifications: An Ontological Journey**” with **Dr. Admir Jukan** in a session led by **Dr. Paresh Rathod**.

Events

CUSTODES at IOSEC 2024

The **International Workshop on Information & Operational Technology (IT & OT) Security Systems (IOSEC 2024)** took place from September 2 - 4, 2024, supported by the **CUSTODES** project.

CUSTODES Plenary Meeting

On September 11-12, 2024, the **CUSTODES** consortium gathered for its **2nd plenary meeting** in Athens, hosted by **AEGIS IT RESEARCH**. Over the course of two intensive days, participants from all partner organizations came together to review the project's progress and strategize for the future.

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New Publications

CUSTODES at 2024 IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience

The paper “**Strengthening Cybersecurity Certifications through Robust Chain of Custody Practices**”, authored by **Dr. Jasmin Cosic (DEKRA SE)**, **Dr. Admir Jukan (AEGIS IT Research GmbH)** and **Prof. Miroslav Baca (University of North)** is published in conference proceeding in “**2024 IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience (IEEE CSR)**” as a research outcome of recent **CUSTODES** activities.

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Upcoming Events

Advanced Telecoms & IoT Summit

The event aims to promote innovative solutions, applications and services that utilize advanced telecommunications infrastructures, such as 5G networks, fiber optic networks to the building (FTTH/B), wireless broadband networks (FWA), IoT, underwater fiber optic networks, satellites, etc. The Advanced Telecoms & IoT Summit 2024 will take place on October 8, 2024 at Zappeion Megaro, Athens.

InfoCom World 2024. Digital Greece: Time for a Leap! Conference

InfoCom World 2024 will take place on November 12, 2024 at the Divani Caravel Hotel, under the guarantee and credibility of Smart Press. The annual meeting of the market for Technology, Information Technology and Telecommunications, will focus on the dynamic development of the country through the adoption and exploitation of new technologies, the challenges and opportunities that arise, and the steps that must be taken by market stakeholders, to implement the “digital leap”!

International Information Security Meeting (ENISE)

ENISE (International Information Security Meeting) Has become the leading international event in Spain for the cybersecurity industry. The eighteenth edition will connect key professionals in the sector, offering different networking spaces and a programme full of activities.

The Consortium

The project unites 16 partners from 11 countries: Sweden, Germany, France, Italy, Belgium, Ireland, Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Netherlands, Switzerland, encompassing the necessary expertise to successfully accomplish the project's ambitious goals.

Secure analytics for the interconnected world

KEY FACTS

Title:	A Certification approach for dynamic, agile and reUSable assessmentT fOr composite systems of ICT proDucts, servicEs, and processeS
Acronym:	CUSTODES
GA No:	101120684
Start:	October 2023
End:	30 September 2026
Topic:	HORIZON-CL3-2022-CS-01-04
Type of action:	Innovation Action (IA)

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